

Addressing Capacity Scaling and Programmability in Future Optical Networks

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Abstract—The increasing demand on data and connectivity is driving the development of new approaches capable of meeting the stringent requirements of future optical networks, in terms of high capacity, bandwidth and energy-efficiency. In this work, the challenges of adopting multi-band (MB) and space division multiplexing (SDM) technologies to enhance capacity and efficiency in optical networks are addressed. Innovative transceiver and switching options are discussed with special focus on flexibility and programmability towards integration with a software defined networking (SDN) control plane.

Index Terms—Software defined networking (SDN), optical networks, multi-band (MB), spatial division multiplexing (SDM)

I. INTRODUCTION

Driven by the the increasing global traffic and the emergence of new services, advancements in transmission and switching solutions capable of meeting performance goals in terms of capacity, bandwidth, cost-efficiency and flexibility should be investigated to foster transition to 6G networks. On this regard, MB and SDM technologies allow to significantly enhance network capacity by exploiting additional bands beyond the conventional C-band and spatial channels, respectively. On the one hand, MB is a promising technology that takes advantage of the use of enhanced spectra including E-, O-, S-, L- and U-bands, to extend the available resources and lifetime of the current optical fiber infrastructure to maximize capital and operational expenditures. However, MB transmission is limited to non linear effects such as Raman scattering that has to be taken into account in the design of the wideband optical systems, as leads to power transfer between

wavelengths [1]. Additionally, new devices such as filters and amplifiers operating in a particular or multiple band(s), should be adopted for successful operation/transmission. This can imply the use of simple band pass filters or even programmable wavelength selective switches (WSS) trading of complexity, cost and flexibility. However, the availability of commercial WSS operating across multiple optical bands is limited and an integrated solution including multiple WSS working in a particular range of wavelengths should be adopted [2]. Several amplifier technologies such as Raman, rare-earth doped amplifiers, bismuth-doped fiber amplifiers and semiconductor amplifiers, are available for signal amplification in different wavelength bands in order to span data transmission and capacity balancing cost and performance [3]. The most appropriate option can be selected according to the targeted application and network segment.

On the other hand, SDM is envisioned as a key solution for expanding network capacity by leveraging parallel transmission across multiple spatial channels. This can be achieved by means of bundles of fibers or special fibers, such as multicore fiber (MCF) and few mode fibers. However, SDM transmission is limited by the crosstalk between adjacent spatial channels, which can be compensated with digital signal processing (DSP) by the implementation of multiple-input multiple-output techniques. Additionally, amplification for SDM transmission is also a challenge and new approaches based on SDM amplifiers for collective amplification of all the spatial channels are investigated in the literature [4].

So, innovative transceiver and switching architectures should be implemented to enable multi-band over spatial division multiplexing (MBoSDM) operation with the appropriate technology option [2], [5]. Hence, a modular MBoSDM sliceable bandwidth/bit rate variable transceivers (S-BVTs) and MBoSDM nodes are proposed in [2] as key devices to increase network capacity and resources. Here, we review these solutions with special focus on programmability and

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Fig. 1. MBoSDM scenario including: (a) transceiver and (b) switching prototypes and (c) S-band, (d) C-band and (e) L-band OFDM received spectra.

reconfigurability toward integration to a software defined networking (SDN) control plane. SDN will enable on-demand reconfiguration of the transceiver and network nodes to dynamically adapt the transmission to the network condition fostering network automation.

II. ADOPTING MB AND SDM IN OPTICAL NETWORKS

Fig. 1, shows the envisioned MBoSDM scenario. New transmission and switching solutions for MBoSDM optical networks are adopted to address the required network capacity scaling facilitating the adoption of 6G. At the transmission part, an innovative MBoSDM S-BVT with 3 slices operating at the S-, C- and L-bands is considered [2]. An advanced switching prototype is also included to enable spectral (band and wavelength) and spatial (core) granularities [2].

A. Transmission solutions for MBoSDM networks

The MBoSDM S-BVT, with enhanced capabilities have been proposed in [2] to enable MB, point-to-point (P2P) and point-to-multi point (P2MP) operation (see Fig. 1). Specifically, the transceiver prototype (Fig. 1 (a)) creates a S+C+L high capacity flow that it is aggregated by means of a band pass filter. At the network nodes, the slices/contributions can be disaggregated and transmitted over different paths, including for example spatial channels, to the same or different end points. The transceiver building blocks consider an array of tuneable laser sources (TLS), which are set to 1500 nm (S-band), 1550.12 nm (C-band) and 1600 nm (L-band), as can be identified in Fig. 1 (c), (d) and (e), where the received optical spectra are depicted. Each bandwidth/bit rate variable transmitter (BVTx) also includes an array of Mach Zehnder modulators (MZM) working at the quadrature point. At the DSP level, adaptive modulation based on orthogonal frequency division multiplexing (OFDM) is implemented and 20 GHz signals are uploaded to a digital-to-analog converter (DAC) at 64 GSa/s. Hence, variable number of bits and power levels can be set to each subcarrier optimizing the overall performance in

terms of capacity/reach [2]. At the receiver side, a band pass filter (BPF) is included to distribute the different slices to the corresponding bandwidth/bit rate variable receiver (BVRx), which is based on direct detection (DD). Different amplification technologies are explored according to the band of operation. Erbium-doped fiber amplifiers (EDFA) are used for the C- and L-bands, whereas thulium-doped fiber amplifier (TDFA) is considered for the S-band. After a filtering stage, the different MB OFDM contributions are photodetected with simple P-type, intrinsic and N-type (PIN) photodiodes. The original data is retrieved by means of an analog-to-digital converter (ADC) at 100 GSa/s and offline receiver DSP. The received double side band (DSB) OFDM spectra, after amplification is monitored with a high-resolution optical spectrum analyzer prototype for the S+C+L-bands, as depicted in the insets of Fig. 1. Successful MB transmission at 120 Gb/s can be achieved in a back-to-back configuration with uniform loading, using quadrature amplitude modulation (QAM) format with 2 bits per symbol. A target bit error rate (BER) of 4.62×10^{-3} is ensured, which corresponds to a 7% hard decision forward error correction (HD-FEC). Additionally, adaptive loading enhances the performance achieving 197 Gb/s aggregated capacity at the target BER, corresponding to 70 Gb/s (C-band), 63 Gb/s (S-band) and 64 Gb/s (L-band). Thanks to the modular and scalable transceiver architecture, additional building blocks can be enabled in different wavelength bands according to the network needs and following a pay-as-you grow approach towards enabling multi Tb/s transmission [2]. The capacity can be further scaled by transmitting over an SDM channel.

B. Switching solutions for MBoSDM optical networks

An innovative MBoSDM node prototype has been designed to enhance switching capabilities to exploit SDM, MB and dense wavelength division multiplexing (DWDM) [2]. The node architecture includes key devices such as BPFs (for band switching), fan-in/-out with a MCF (for SDM switching) and

100 GHz arrayed-waveguide gratings and programmable WSS of 12.5 GHz granularity (for wavelength switching). Additionally, the core of the node consists of a 18X18 matrix which enables different node operations and add/drop functionality. The MBoSDM node is integrated in the ADRENALINE testbed, as seen in Fig. 1. The ADRENALINE testbed is a photonic mesh network with 4 nodes (N1 to N4 in Fig. 1) based on reconfigurable optical add-drop multiplexers (ROADM) and optical cross connects and connected by bidirectional links of standard single mode fiber (SMF), covering a total distance of 600 km [7]. N1 is connected to 4 cores (2 per direction) of a 19-cores MCF of 25.4 km. N5 and N7 virtual MBoSDM nodes and N6 virtual ROADM node are considered to showcase dynamic service provisioning in a MBoSDM network (see Figs. 1 and 3).

III. ENABLING SDN CAPABILITIES

The programmability and reconfiguration of transceivers, ROADMs, amplifiers, and other optical devices are key towards enabling autonomous networking for an efficient manage of network resources. To this end, the SDN paradigm can be adopted to facilitate dynamic control and remote configuration of the different network elements. Different programmable parameters and devices of the proposed transceiver MBoSDM S-BVT (introduced in section II-A) can be reconfigured according to the network condition by means of a centralized SDN control plane. Specifically, the OpenConfig open and vendor-neutral data model is adopted for the implementation of SDN agents in order to foster network disaggregation [8]. The wavelength and power of the TLS in each S-BVT building block can be configured to operate in a specific wavelength band, and the DAC and ADC output ports can also be enabled/disabled. Fig. 2, shows the successful configuration of each transmitter and receiver MBoSDM S-BVT building block. First the S-band slice is established, followed by the C-band and L-band transceivers. After configuring each receiver the signal to noise (SNR) per subcarrier vector and BER are calculated, ensuring the target FEC.

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[2025-01-22 12:41:30,866] DEBUG in sbvt_agent.py: Optical Channel channel-102 configured with freq: 199861639 and power_laser: 0.0
[2025-01-22 12:41:30,866] DEBUG in sbvt_agent.py: TX configured
[2025-01-22 12:39:39,928] DEBUG in sbvt_agent.py: [[23.26014706335313, 135.30451359836964, 169.84801620772288, ...] → SNR
... → BER S-band
[2025-01-22 12:39:39,936] DEBUG in sbvt_agent.py: RX configured
[2025-01-22 12:45:31,936] DEBUG in sbvt_agent.py: Optical Channel channel-101 configured with freq: 193399516 and power_laser: 6.5
[2025-01-22 12:45:31,936] DEBUG in sbvt_agent.py: TX configured
[2025-01-22 12:48:12,258] DEBUG in sbvt_agent.py: [[15.776882817488226, 247.80455979021878, 193.8646735696744, ...] → SNR
... → BER C-band
[2025-01-22 12:48:12,266] DEBUG in sbvt_agent.py: RX configured
[2025-01-22 12:59:14,216] DEBUG in sbvt_agent.py: Optical Channel channel-103 configured with freq: 187370286 and power_laser: 0.0
[2025-01-22 12:59:14,216] DEBUG in sbvt_agent.py: TX configured
[2025-01-22 13:04:53,505] DEBUG in sbvt_agent.py: [[45.33745650162614, 49.431525634207595, 49.76801958980613, ...] → SNR
... → BER L-band
[2025-01-22 13:04:53,512] DEBUG in sbvt_agent.py: RX configured

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Fig. 2. MBoSDM S-BVT configuration by means of SDN agents.

Finally, a dynamic service provisioning in a MBoSDM network is demonstrated including both the MBoSDM S-BVT and the MBoSDM node prototypes (detailed in sections II-A and II-B). Different node operations are defined including core, band and wavelength switching and spectrum add/drop. Fig. 3 shows the SDN controller GUI with the different

established connections including the ADRENALINE nodes with the MBoSDM node prototype (N1, N3 and N4), the 2 emulated MBoSDM nodes (N5 and N7), 1 emulated ROADM node (N6) and the MBoSDM S-BVT node. An example of spectrum and core assignment for the different established links is shown in the inset of the figure.

Fig. 3. SDN controller GUI showing the validation of the MBoSDM scenario. Links show freq. slots (DWDM) and core allocation (SDM).

IV. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper we review relevant transmission and switching options based on the MBoSDM S-BVT and a MBoSDM node prototypes to enhance network capacity scaling towards 6G. The proposed programmable transceiver can dynamically enable MB P2P and P2MP connections and presents a modular architecture that can be upgraded and reconfigured by means of SDN agents according to the network requirements. L+C+S transmission has successfully been setup for an aggregated capacity of 197 Gb/s at the target BER. Additionally, a MBoSDM scenario has been validated, at the control plane level, including the MBoSDM S-BVT and MBoSDM nodes.

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